

Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America

Crustal Attenuation and Site Amplification Across the Central and Eastern United States from Lg Q Tomography

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	
Article Type:	Article
Section/Category:	Regular Issue
Full Title:	Crustal Attenuation and Site Amplification Across the Central and Eastern United States from Lg Q Tomography
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Abstract:	<p>We present a new high-resolution model of crustal Lg-wave attenuation and site amplification across the Central and Eastern United States (CEUS), derived from joint tomographic inversions of vertical and horizontal seismic amplitudes. Using more than 75,000 broadband records from over 1,600 regional crustal earthquakes ($M_w \geq 3.5$, depth < 30 km) recorded between 2007 and 2024 at more than 1,500 seismic stations, including data from the EarthScope Transportable Array (TA), N4, and other regional networks, we resolve frequency-dependent seismic quality factor (Q), site terms, and source amplitudes across five center frequencies from 0.7 to 11.3 Hz. Our results show significant lateral variations in attenuation, with Q_0 values as low as ~ 200–230 in sediment-rich, tectonically complex regions such as the Mississippi Embayment, Gulf and Atlantic Coastal Plains, and the Southern Oklahoma Aulacogen. In contrast, stable cratonic interiors such as the Permian Basin and Midcontinent exhibit high Q_0 values (up to ~ 380), reflecting cold, uniform basement crust. We also resolve frequency dependence of attenuation via the η parameter, which varies from ~ 0.7 in high-Q_0 regions to > 1.0 in areas with strong scattering. Site amplification terms show higher values in intracratonic basins and coastal plain sediments and lower values in regions with exposed or shallow bedrock. The horizontal-to-vertical site amplification ratio exhibits a polarity shift across the Coastal Plain boundary. This shift reflects the contrast in near-surface geology between flat-lying sediments and folded orogenic crust. Checkerboard and feature recovery tests demonstrate the model's resolution capacity down to ~ 100 km, and jackknife resampling confirms relative uncertainties below 2% across most of the domain. Compared to previous CEUS attenuation studies, our model benefits from denser station-event coverage and improved inversion methodology. These findings provide critical input for refining seismic hazard assessments and updating ground motion prediction models for the next-generation U.S. National Seismic Hazard Model.</p>
Author Comments:	
Suggested Reviewers:	
Opposed Reviewers:	
Additional Information:	
Question	Response
Key Point #1: <i>Three key points will be printed at the front of your manuscript so readers can get a quick overview. Please provide three	CEUS attenuation and site response remain uncertain due to limited data and poor path coverage.

<p>COMPLETE sentences addressing the following: 1) state the problem you are addressing in a FULL sentence; 2) state your main conclusion(s) in a FULL sentence; and 3) state the broader implications of your findings in a FULL sentence. Each point must be 110 characters or less (including spaces).</p>	
<p>Key Point #2:</p>	<p>Lg-wave tomography yields detailed, frequency-dependent maps of Q and site response across the CEUS.</p>
<p>Key Point #3:</p>	<p>Improves CEUS ground motion models, aiding hazard assessment and resilient infrastructure planning.</p>

1 **Crustal Attenuation and Site Amplification Across the Central and**
2 **Eastern United States from Lg Q Tomography**

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18 **Problem:** Seismic attenuation and site response across the CEUS are poorly constrained due to
19 limited path coverage and resolution, hindering accurate ground motion prediction.

20 **Conclusion:** Using joint Lg-wave amplitude tomography, we produce the most detailed and
21 frequency-dependent maps of crustal attenuation (Q) and site amplification to date for the CEUS.

22 **Broader Implications:** Our results enhance path- and site-specific ground motion models,
23 supporting improved seismic hazard assessments and infrastructure resilience planning across the
24 CEUS.

26 **Abstract**

27 We present a new high-resolution model of crustal Lg-wave attenuation and site amplification
28 across the Central and Eastern United States (CEUS), derived from joint tomographic inversions
29 of vertical and horizontal seismic amplitudes. Using more than 75,000 broadband records from
30 over 1,600 regional crustal earthquakes ($M_w \geq 3.5$, depth < 30 km) recorded between 2007 and
31 2024 at more than 1,500 seismic stations, including data from the EarthScope Transportable Array
32 (TA), N4, and other regional networks, we resolve frequency-dependent seismic quality factor (Q),
33 site terms, and source amplitudes across five center frequencies from 0.7 to 11.3 Hz. Our results
34 show significant lateral variations in attenuation, with Q_0 values as low as ~ 200 – 230 in sediment-
35 rich, tectonically complex regions such as the Mississippi Embayment, Gulf and Atlantic Coastal
36 Plains, and the Southern Oklahoma Aulacogen. In contrast, stable cratonic interiors such as the
37 Permian Basin and Midcontinent exhibit high Q_0 values (up to ~ 380), reflecting cold, uniform
38 basement crust. We also resolve frequency dependence of attenuation via the η parameter, which
39 varies from ~ 0.7 in high- Q_0 regions to > 1.0 in areas with strong scattering. Site amplification terms
40 show higher values in intracratonic basins and coastal plain sediments and lower values in regions
41 with exposed or shallow bedrock. The horizontal-to-vertical site amplification ratio exhibits a
42 polarity shift across the Coastal Plain boundary. This shift reflects the contrast in near-surface
43 geology between flat-lying sediments and folded orogenic crust. Checkerboard and feature
44 recovery tests demonstrate the model's resolution capacity down to ~ 100 km, and jackknife
45 resampling confirms relative uncertainties below 2% across most of the domain. Compared to
46 previous CEUS attenuation studies, our model benefits from denser station-event coverage and
47 improved inversion methodology. These findings provide critical input for refining seismic hazard
48 assessments and updating ground motion prediction models for the next-generation U.S. National
49 Seismic Hazard Model.

50

51 **1.0 Introduction**

52 The CEUS faces significant seismic hazards due to its high population density and extensive
53 critical infrastructure, despite lower seismicity rates than the Western United States (WUS). The
54 rate at which shaking due to an earthquake decreases with distance—termed seismic attenuation—
55 is one of the most important factors in CEUS seismic hazard. In particular, low attenuation
56 characterizes much of the CEUS crust, allowing seismic waves to travel great distances with
57 minimal energy loss and ultimately increasing ground motion intensity. Attenuation is not uniform
58 across the CEUS, however. For example, thick sedimentary deposits found in the Mississippi
59 Embayment (ME), Gulf Coastal Plain (GCP), and Atlantic Coastal Plain (ACP) attenuate shaking.
60 Nevertheless, these same deposits and their contrast with the underlying bedrock can cause
61 resonances that can locally amplify shaking relative to bedrock sites. Together, the spatial
62 heterogeneity in both attenuation and site response presents a complex and poorly constrained
63 challenge for ground-motion prediction and seismic hazard modeling in the CEUS (Cramer, 2017;
64 Chapman & Conn, 2016; Pratt & Schleicher, 2021; Boyd et al., 2022).

65 Previous regional attenuation studies have provided valuable insights into attenuation and its
66 inverse, the seismic quality factor Q . Still, these investigations were geographically limited by
67 sparse station coverage, limited data from local or regional earthquakes, or insufficient spatial
68 resolution. For instance, Gallegos et al. (2014) used two-station and reverse two-station L_g
69 tomography to image central U.S. crustal Q , but coverage and resolution were restricted. The
70 Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center’s Next Generation Attenuation-East (NGA-East)
71 project revisited regional attenuation but identified significant unresolved areas, notably the highly
72 populated ACP (Dreiling et al., 2014). Others (Chapman and Conn, 2016; Cramer, 2017) focused
73 primarily on southeastern US and Gulf Coast attenuation using relatively sparse earthquake data.
74 More recently, Levandowski et al. (2021) used earthquakes from 2010 to 2016 to detail crustal
75 attenuation near the WUS-CEUS but did not thoroughly image the eastern U.S. Recognizing these
76 limitations, our study provides the first comprehensive crustal attenuation tomography and site
77 amplification quantification covering the entire CEUS, leveraging the expansive datasets from the
78 EarthScope Transportable Array (TA) and the recently commissioned N4 network. These
79 networks offer extensive, uniformly distributed seismic recordings from regional-distance

80 earthquakes (~150–1500 km) that significantly enhance our capability to resolve spatial variations
81 in seismic attenuation and site amplification.

82 Most previous broad Q tomography studies focused on vertical amplitudes because of their
83 generally higher signal-to-noise ratios (Levandowski et al., 2021; Mahanama and Cramer, 2023;
84 Zhao et al., 2010). However, earthquake damage and seismic hazard assessments necessitate an
85 understanding of horizontal ground motions (Bent & Delahaye, 2007). Therefore, we have
86 analyzed both vertical and horizontal components of recorded seismic waveforms, addressing a
87 critical gap. Our research employs joint tomographic inversions of regional Lg ground-motion
88 amplitudes for $1/Q$, site amplification, and source amplitude. Joint tomography uniquely allows
89 explicit separation of the effects of crustal attenuation, source amplitude, and site response, and
90 determination of their frequency dependences and spatial variations.

91 The choice the of Lg seismic phase for tomographic inversion is particularly suited to the CEUS
92 because of the unique propagation characteristics of Lg. Lg waves, comprising shear waves
93 trapped in the continental crust, dominate seismic signals at regional distances (>100 km) and
94 frequencies above approximately 0.5 Hz, and their amplitudes decay predominantly due to crustal
95 attenuation (Erickson et al., 2004; Gallegos et al., 2017; McNamara et al., 2014). These waves
96 have been reliably observed at distances of thousands of kilometers in stable continental regions
97 worldwide (e.g., McNamara & Walter, 2001), making them particularly effective for crustal Q
98 tomography in seismically quiet but geographically extensive areas like the CEUS. Furthermore,
99 long Lg raypaths allow each earthquake to be recorded by numerous stations, and allow each
100 station to record many earthquakes, thus enhancing the robustness of inversion results and the
101 separation of source, path, and site effects (Phillips et al., 2014; Levandowski et al., 2021;
102 Mahanama & Carmer, 2023).

103 Attenuation and site-response variations arise from the complex geological and tectonic setting of
104 the CEUS, a region characterized largely by stable continental crust but interspersed with
105 significant geological contrasts, including the Appalachian and Grenville orogenic provinces,
106 major sedimentary basins, and the extensive Coastal Plains (Mooney & Kaban, 2010; Yassminh et
107 al., 2019). Crustal attenuation is not uniform across eastern North America, as demonstrated by
108 previous targeted studies (Chun et al., 1987; Shi et al., 1996; Perry et al., 2020; Cramer and Powell,

109 2021). For example, marked differences in attenuation have been documented at geological
110 boundaries such as the Grenville-Appalachian transition and within sediment-rich coastal regions.
111 Unresolved attenuation features beneath the ACP (Eulenfeld and Wegler, 2017; Gallegos et al.,
112 2014) further underscore the importance of a detailed regional investigation. Recent seismic events
113 such as the 2020 Mw 5.1 Sparta, North Carolina (Figueiredo et al., 2022) and April 2024 Mw 4.8
114 Tewksbury, New Jersey earthquakes (Boyd et al., 2024) have highlighted new opportunities for
115 attenuation imaging in previously under-studied regions of the CEUS. These events, coupled with
116 expanded seismic networks since 2016, provide a richer dataset for refining attenuation models
117 and improving our understanding of regional seismic hazard across the CEUS.

118 In summary, the specific objectives of this research include producing high-resolution, frequency-
119 dependent maps of crustal Q across the CEUS and characterizing the frequency-dependent site
120 amplification for both horizontal and vertical seismic motions. Achieving these objectives will
121 address key limitations in spatial coverage and resolution, reducing uncertainty in seismic hazard
122 assessments of the National Seismic Hazard Model (NSHM). By incorporating localized variations
123 in crustal attenuation and site response, our findings will directly contribute to improved seismic
124 risk mitigation strategies, benefiting local, regional, and national infrastructure planning efforts
125 aligned with USGS goals.

126 **2.0 Approach**

127 **2.1 Data Set & Processing**

128 We constructed a high-quality seismic data set using regional earthquake waveforms to perform
129 comprehensive crustal attenuation and site amplification tomography across the CEUS. Waveform
130 data were acquired from the Incorporated Research Institutions for Seismology (IRIS) Data
131 Management Center (DMC), covering crustal earthquakes (depth < 30 km) with magnitudes M_w
132 ≥ 3.5 recorded during the period from 2007 to 2024 (Fig. 1a). Data were collected from stations
133 in the epicentral distances range between approximately 150 and 1,500 km. This distance window
134 was chosen explicitly to avoid contamination of the Lg seismic phase by other seismic phases
135 (Phillips et al., 2014).

136 Waveform data underwent rigorous quality control measures. We inspected waveforms for clear
137 Lg arrivals on all three components (vertical, north-south, and east-west) and implemented a strict
138 pre-phase signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) threshold criterion. Specifically, a time window for the Lg
139 signal was selected based on group velocities between 3.0 and 3.6 km/s, and a noise window was
140 extracted from the P-wave coda section (group velocities of 4.8-5.8 km/s), ensuring equal
141 durations for noise and signal windows (Fig. 2a). The signal amplitude spectrum was corrected for
142 noise by assuming that the observed waveform represents a linear superposition of the true Lg
143 signal and noise, which are presumed to be uncorrelated. Thus, we isolated the true Lg-wave
144 amplitude spectrum by subtracting the noise spectrum from the observed spectrum (Fig. 2b) (Xie
145 and Mitchell, 1990; Zhao et al., 2010). A threshold SNR at 2.0 was applied to ensure data
146 reliability, removing spectral data points below this threshold (Fig. 2c). This rigorous criterion
147 effectively excluded waveforms contaminated by noise (McNamara, 2000; Pasyanos et al., 2009).

148 Following these steps, instrument response functions were deconvolved from the velocity
149 seismograms, which were then integrated to obtain absolute ground displacement measurements
150 in meters. For spectral analysis, we extended each window by adding a 10% duration interval on
151 both ends and applied cosine tapers to minimize spectral leakage. The displacement time series
152 were transformed into the frequency domain through a Fourier transform, allowing us to measure
153 spectral amplitudes in terms of root mean squared (RMS) values across non-overlapping octave-
154 wide frequency bands.

155 We performed spectral analysis across five distinct frequency bands centered at 0.7, 1.4, 2.8, 5.6,
156 and 11.3 Hz, corresponding respectively to the frequency ranges of 0.5–1, 1–2, 2–4, 4–8, and 8–
157 16 Hz. Measuring RMS amplitudes rather than peak amplitudes significantly reduces sensitivity
158 to outliers, thus enhancing the stability and reliability of our spectral measurements.

159 An overdetermined solution is ensured by redundancy: Each event included in the dataset is
160 recorded on at least four seismic stations, and each station records at least four events. After
161 applying the selection criteria, our finalized dataset includes over 1,600 unique earthquakes
162 recorded at more than 1,500 unique seismic stations, combining both vertical and horizontal
163 datasets. Figure 1a illustrates the distribution of events and stations for the vertical and horizontal
164 components at 0.7 Hz. The raypath coverage is dominated by contributions from the combined TA

165 and N4 networks, with approximately 50% of the total raypaths originating from stations
166 belonging to these two networks. Notably, many of the selected events and stations extend
167 westward beyond the CEUS into the Intermountain West (IMW), allowing us to leverage long-
168 path Lg observations for cross-regional comparisons and improved resolution near the CEUS
169 boundary.

170 Due to the decrease in seismic amplitudes (and consequently signal-to-noise ratios) at higher
171 frequencies, the number of usable observations decreases with increasing frequency. The vertical-
172 component dataset consists of 47,734 records at 0.7 Hz, 44,395 at 1.4 Hz, 39,003 at 2.8 Hz, 28,669
173 at 5.8 Hz, and 28,556 at 11.3 Hz (Fig. 3a). For horizontal components, the dataset includes 20,742
174 records at 0.7 Hz, 20,101 at 1.4 Hz, 17,783 at 2.8 Hz, 11,746 at 5.6 Hz, and 8475 at 11.3 Hz (Fig.
175 3b). This gradual reduction in raypath density with frequency leads to a corresponding decrease in
176 spatial resolution in the higher-frequency tomographic inversions. Figure 4 presents a raypath
177 density map gridded at $50 \text{ km} \times 50 \text{ km}$ resolution, showing the number of raypaths intersecting
178 each grid cell matching the inversion grid resolution which highlights the spatial sampling density
179 used in our tomography for 0.7 Hz.

180 The final dataset resulting from careful event selection, meticulous quality control, and stringent
181 SNR-based filtering provides a robust basis for high-resolution tomographic imaging of crustal
182 attenuation and site amplification across the CEUS. We closely followed the approach outlined by
183 Zhao et al. (2010) for processing regional Lg waveforms. For a comprehensive description of these
184 procedures, readers are referred to Zhao et al. (2010).

185

186 **2.2 Amplitude Decomposition and Inversion Framework**

187 To explicitly separate the observed Lg amplitudes at each center frequency (f) into contributions
188 from source excitation, site amplification, and attenuation, we model the recorded amplitude as
189 the product of four components: energy loss due to geometrical spreading, an event-specific source
190 term, a station-specific site term, and an exponential decay term representing frequency-dependent
191 attenuation (Herrmann and Kijko, 1983; Brune, 1970):

192 $A_{ij}(f) = D_{ij}^{-\gamma} S_j(f) R_i(f) e^{-\pi f D_{ij} / Q v}$ (2.1)

193 Here, D_{ij} is the hypocentral distance from earthquake j to station i . $S_j(f)$ is the source amplitude
 194 at frequency f , and $R_i(f)$ is the site-specific amplification factor. The geometrical spreading
 195 exponent γ is set to 0.5, consistent with previous regional studies (McNamara et al., 2014; Benz et
 196 al., 1997), and the average crustal shear-wave velocity v is taken as 3.5 km/s, appropriate for Lg
 197 wave propagation in the CEUS. The attenuation is described by the quality factor Q , assumed to
 198 be frequency-dependent.

199 By taking the natural logarithm of Equation (2.1), the relation becomes linear and suitable for
 200 inversion:

201 $\ln(A_{ij}) + \gamma \ln(D_{ij}) = \ln(S_j) + \ln(R_i) - \left(\frac{\pi f D_{ij}}{v}\right) 1/Q$ (2.2)

202 The terms on the left-hand side are known or derived from data, while the right-hand side contains
 203 the unknown source term (S_j) site term (R_i), and the attenuation term ($1/Q$). The site response R
 204 acts as a scalar multiplier, which indicates amplification for $\ln(R) > 0$ and damping for $\ln(R) < 0$
 205 relative to a reference station with $\ln(R_{ref}) = 0$, approximately the median site response at that
 206 frequency. The dependence of the logarithmic amplitude on distance allows the slope to be
 207 interpreted as a direct measure of attenuation, with larger Q values corresponding to gentler slopes.

208

209 **2.3 Tomographic Inversion and Finite-Width Sensitivity**

210 For the tomographic inversion, the study area is parameterized by a set of k spatial nodes that
 211 define a 2D-continuous model of $1/Q$. This node-based formulation replaces traditional
 212 discretization into internally uniform grid cells and allows attenuation to vary smoothly between
 213 nodes. Each observed amplitude is modeled as a path-integrated contribution from all nodes
 214 traversed by the ray path between source j and receiver i , with path segments through each node
 215 denoted D_{ijk} . The model becomes:

216 $\ln(A_{ij}) + r \ln(D_{ij}) = \ln(S_j) + \ln(R_i) - \left(\frac{\pi f}{v}\right) \sum_1^k D_{ijk} / Q_k \quad (2.3)$

217 A key feature of the tomographic approach adopted in this study, which follows the methodology
 218 introduced by Levandowski et al. (2021), is the incorporation of finite-width sensitivity kernels.
 219 Unlike traditional ray theory, which assumes infinitely thin sensitivity only along the great-circle
 220 path, we acknowledge that Lg energy arriving within a finite time window around the direct path
 221 influences the observed RMS amplitude. These kernels are conceptually similar to Fresnel zones.
 222 The spatial sensitivity to a point depends inversely on the adjoint travel time (source-to-anomaly-
 223 to-receiver). For example, if a point along a nearby path contributes energy arriving halfway
 224 through a 20 s window (i.e., the adjoint travel time is 10 s longer than the direct ray's travel time),
 225 its influence is weighted at 50% relative to the direct path. This formulation reflects the reality that
 226 off-path heterogeneity affects the observed amplitudes during the Lg time window. As a result, the
 227 final term in Equation (2.3) becomes a surface integral rather than a strict summation along the
 228 direct raypath. These finite-width kernels enhance the realism and resolution of the inversion, by
 229 taking advantage of forward-scattered Lg energy that arrives within the time window
 230 (Levandowski et al., 2021).

231 Lateral variations in $1/Q$ are regularized using a frequency-dependent smoothing matrix, where
 232 the weights applied to differences in $1/Q$ between neighboring nodes k and k' are proportional to
 233 frequency f and inversely related to the node separation $D_{kk'}$. A leading coefficient for this
 234 regularization term was selected through L-curve Tikhonov analysis, with a value of
 235 approximately $\sim 35f$ providing optimal trade-offs between model norm and residual misfit across
 236 all frequencies.

237 Inversions were performed independently for each of the five frequency bands using the singular
 238 value decomposition algorithm of Levandowski et al. (2021), with node spacing set at ~ 50 km.
 239 The data vector consisted of amplitude residuals computed relative to a reference model with
 240 spatially uniform Q and source terms. Graphically, the reference model is represented by the best-
 241 fit lines in Figure 3, and these residuals are represented by the scatter of points in Figure 3 around
 242 the best-fit line at a given frequency. The vertical distances between the line and points are the
 243 sum of the respective R terms, variations in source amplitudes S, and variations in path-integrated
 244 $1/Q$.

245 Finally, once the five independent frequency-specific inversions are completed, the frequency
246 dependence of Q at each model node is modeled as a power-law with exponent η (e.g., Fig. 5):

$$247 \quad Q_{Lg}(f) = Q_0 f^\eta \quad (2.4)$$

248 This relationship allows us to present frequency-dependent attenuation in the CEUS, providing
249 physically interpretable maps of crustal heterogeneity relevant to ground-motion prediction and
250 hazard modeling.

251 **3.0 Results**

252 **3.1 Results Overview**

253 To evaluate spatial variations in crustal attenuation and site amplification across the CEUS, we
254 analyzed the results of independently inverted tomographic models at five central frequencies and
255 for both vertical and horizontal amplitude data, as described in the Data Set & Processing section.
256 These inversions yield frequency-specific estimates of Q , source, and site terms for horizontal and
257 vertical components.

258 As anticipated, resolution decreases with increasing frequency due to the reduction in usable Lg
259 observations, which results from declining signal-to-noise ratios. This trend is clearly evident in
260 the checkerboard recovery results shown in Figure S5, where higher-frequency inversions exhibit
261 diminished ability to resolve small-scale features.

262 Given their superior data coverage and reliability, the vertical-component Q models serve as the
263 primary basis for interpreting spatial attenuation trends throughout the CEUS and its surroundings.
264 Unless explicitly stated, all subsequent discussions refer to vertical-component results. Horizontal-
265 component results are used complementarily to assess whether similar attenuation patterns appear
266 despite fewer usable paths due to lower SNR. Q maps from horizontal and vertical components
267 show substantial overlap in both anomaly location and magnitude, particularly in the low to mid-
268 frequency range (≤ 3 Hz), where path coverage is highest (Fig. S2 & S3). The presence of major
269 anomalies in both components underscores the stability of the tomographic output across
270 components.

271

272 To improve resolution further, we performed additional inversions combining vertical and
273 horizontal raypaths into a unified dataset. This yielded denser ray coverage, especially in regions
274 where either vertical or horizontal data alone were insufficient (Fig. S1a). However, vertical-
275 component results remain the principal dataset for interpreting attenuation structure and validating
276 geologic correlations. Given that the spatial distribution of attenuation anomalies remains
277 consistent across all five central frequencies, our subsequent interpretations focus primarily on the
278 Q_0 (1 Hz) results for clarity and interpretability (Fig. 6), with accompanying discussion of the
279 frequency-dependence parameter η (Fig. 7). Key features referenced throughout the text are
280 labeled on the attenuation map in Figure 1b.

281 We also broadened the scope of our study westward into the IMW, a region with more extensive
282 previous attenuation work. This expansion serves a dual purpose: (1) to provide context for CEUS
283 attenuation and frequency dependency values (Fig. 6 and 7) by comparing them with those from a
284 tectonically active region and (2) to assess inversion performance in regions where more
285 benchmark models are available. Consistent with expectations, the IMW exhibits lower average
286 Q_0 (~250) relative to the CEUS (~350), reflecting stronger attenuation in more tectonically
287 deformed crust (Phillips et al., 2014; Levandowski et al., 2021; Pasyanos et al., 2009). However,
288 both regions show substantial lateral variation, underscoring the importance of high-resolution,
289 region-specific models for seismic hazard applications.

290 The empirical site-response terms for the vertical and horizontal component, as well as their ratio,
291 H/V, are shown in Figure 8. Resolution tests are presented in Figure 9, 10, and 11 of the main
292 manuscript, as well as in Figures S4, S5, and S6 of the Supplementary Materials. Together, these
293 results provide robust and spatially resolved constraints on frequency-dependent crustal
294 attenuation and site amplification across the CEUS. We now discuss these variations, subdividing
295 the CEUS into two broad regions: the Coastal Plains and Midcontinent.

296 **3. 2 Midcontinent CEUS**

297 We observe significant lateral variability in crustal attenuation across the Midcontinent region of
298 the CEUS (Fig. 6). While the CEUS is characterized by more uniform Q_0 than the tectonically

299 active IMW, the Midcontinent region features several notable exceptions associated with inherited
300 rift structures, intracratonic basins, and sediment-filled troughs.

301 Compared to the IMW, where Q_0 values drop below 220 in zones of active deformation and
302 elevated heat flow (e.g., the Southern Rockies), the Midcontinent shows generally higher Q_0
303 values, consistent with its cratonic, stable lithosphere. However, structurally complex features such
304 as the Southern Oklahoma Aulacogen (SOA), the ME, and the Midcontinent Rift System (MCR)
305 introduce significant heterogeneity in seismic attenuation.

306 One of the most prominent low- Q_0 anomalies is centered on the SOA, where values decline to
307 ~ 230 . This feature reflects an ancient, failed rift system characterized by thick, porous, and fluid-
308 rich sediments and numerous ancestral faults (Chase et al., 2023), conditions that likely enhance
309 both intrinsic attenuation and scattering. Supporting this interpretation, Cramer (2018) observed
310 Q anisotropy along the trend of the Southern Oklahoma Aulacogen (SOA), with lower Q values
311 on ray paths aligned with the trend compared to those crossing it.

312 East of the SOA, the ME represents another major low- Q_0 feature, with values also clustering
313 around ~ 230 . This anomaly aligns spatially with thick sediment accumulations (up to ~ 5 km) and
314 elevated heat flow ranging from 60 to 89 mW/m², although it is less than 60 mW/m² in the northern
315 ME (Blackwell and Richards, 2004; Blackwell et al., 2006). The embayment overlies the Reelfoot
316 Rift and includes the New Madrid Seismic Zone (NMSZ), both of which add tectonic and structural
317 complexity. These factors contribute to both intrinsic energy loss and enhanced scattering,
318 consistent with previous tomographic and ground motion modeling studies (Cramer and Powell,
319 2021).

320 Interestingly, the northern portion of the ME shows higher Q_0 and lower η in the horizontal
321 components than the vertical components (c.f., Figures 6a & 6b, 7a & 7b). Cramer (2018) found
322 higher Q (less attenuation) in this region than to the south. The Alabama-Oklahoma Lineament
323 (AOL), a persistent transform fault from the Precambrian through the Mesozoic, seems associated
324 with this midcontinental to Gulf Coast increase in attenuation (Cramer, 2018). The heat flow
325 transition from lower to higher noted in the previous paragraph (Blackwell and Richards, 2004)
326 also seems associated with the AOL. A similar Q transition appears in the tomographic attenuation

327 results in Figures 6 and 7, more strongly in the horizontal data and the vertical η data than the
328 vertical Q_0 data. Cramer's (2018) regional ray paths are north-south across the ME, while this
329 study's ray paths are dominantly east-west. Nazemi et al. (2017) and Nazemi (2023) used Lg waves
330 from regional earthquakes and body waves from local earthquakes to characterize higher crustal
331 attenuation near the NMSZ and under the embayment using broadband stations in the embayment,
332 similar to this study's results for vertical components (Figure 6a and 7a). Taken together, these
333 studies suggest an azimuthal dependence of Q in the northern ME region, possibly due to increased
334 scattering because of the NMSZ, a dominantly northeast-southwest trending fault system.

335 By contrast, the western arm of the MCR—a failed Proterozoic rift extending from Lake Superior
336 southwestward—displays moderate attenuation, with Q_0 values typically between 270 and 300.
337 The rift is underlain by thick mafic crust, likely the result of reactivation of rift-related structures
338 under compression and flanked by volcanic fill. The contrasts between crystalline rocks near the
339 rift axis with adjacent basins, along-rift variations in magmatism and reactivation, and transform
340 structures (Levandowski et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2016; Shen and Ritzwoller, 2016; Levandowski
341 et al., 2021) result in locally variable Q_0 that includes values as low as ~ 240 and as high as ~ 330 .

342 Additionally, our Q_0 model reveals a southeast-trending feature from southern Michigan through
343 western Ohio and into the Appalachian foreland ($Q_0 \sim 250$). This anomaly may reflect the extended
344 eastern arm of the MCR, specifically the Fort Wayne Rift (FWR), or be associated with Proterozoic
345 basement features such as the Grenville Front. Previous geophysical studies, including ambient
346 noise tomography and receiver function analyses, have suggested crustal thinning and elevated
347 lower crustal temperatures in this region (Homman & Nyblade, 2023; Shen and Ritzwoller, 2016).
348 These crustal variations may enhance seismic attenuation through increased intrinsic absorption
349 or scattering at structural boundaries.

350 Taken together, these localized low- Q_0 anomalies embedded in the high- Q_0 Midcontinent
351 highlight the critical influence of inherited tectonic fabric, sedimentary fill, and thermal structure
352 on crustal attenuation. While much of the CEUS interior maintains $Q_0 \sim 300$ - 330 , consistent with
353 stable cratonic conditions, these exceptions underscore the importance of resolving fine-scale
354 heterogeneity when evaluating seismic hazard and ground-motion behavior across the region.

355 Another striking feature within the Midcontinent CEUS is the broad high- Q_0 anomaly ($Q_0 \sim 360$)
356 spanning central Texas, the Permian Basin, and southeastern New Mexico. This region stands out
357 as one of the most coherent low-attenuation zones in the entire model, suggesting exceptionally
358 efficient Lg-wave propagation. The anomaly coincides with the tectonically quiescent (in terms of
359 natural seismicity) southern Great Plains and Permian Basin provinces, including both the Midland
360 and Delaware sub-basins. These basins are underlain by thick, relatively undeformed Precambrian
361 basement and are filled with stable platform carbonates and evaporites, which tend to support
362 higher Q due to their low intrinsic attenuation and lack of scattering interfaces (Pasyanos et al.,
363 2009; Phillips et al., 2014). Heat flow across this region is exceptionally low (30–50 mW/m²),
364 further reducing intrinsic energy loss (Blackwell and Richards, 2004).

365 Low attenuation here is consistent with findings from other regional and national attenuation
366 models, which also identify the Permian Basin as a high- Q region within the continental interior
367 (Levandowski et al., 2021; Pasyanos et al., 2009). Moreover, seismic velocity models show
368 elevated shear-wave speeds throughout the crust, supporting the interpretation of a cold,
369 compositionally uniform crust (Shen and Ritzwoller, 2016). Unlike many of the low- Q_0 anomalies
370 associated with thick sediment or rift-related structures, the Central Texas–Permian Basin high-
371 Q_0 region likely reflects low intrinsic attenuation in dense, crystalline basement rocks and a lack
372 of crustal fluids. This contrast with surrounding regions, particularly the low- Q_0 Gulf Coast to the
373 southeast underscores the importance of thermal and lithologic controls on crustal seismic energy
374 dissipation.

375 **3. 3 Coastal Plain CEUS**

376 The Coastal Plain of the CEUS, encompassing the GCP and ACP, is marked by strong lateral
377 contrasts in seismic attenuation, crustal structure, and surface geology. This physiographic
378 province shown in Figures 1b, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 11, is delineated using a composite of its major
379 subsections, including the West Gulf Coastal Plain, Mississippi Alluvial Plain, East Gulf Coastal
380 Plain, Floridian section, Sea Island section, and Embayed section (Figure 1b). Formed by
381 successive marine transgressions and continental margin sedimentation, this province overlies a
382 transitional crustal zone between the stable North American craton and the thinned, modified crust
383 of the continental margin. Structurally, the Coastal Plain masks significant terrane boundaries,

384 buried faults, and Proterozoic sutures (e.g., the Suwannee-Wiggins suture zone and Brunswick
385 magnetic anomaly), many of which are relict zones of crustal weakness that may influence present-
386 day seismic wave propagation (Zhao et al., 2010; Whitmeyer and Karlstrom, 2007).

387 Recent studies have delineated the Coastal Plain boundary using frequency-dependent ground
388 motion models, attenuation gradients, and sediment thickness maps. For instance, Cramer (2018)
389 introduced a frequency-dependent Gulf Coast CEUS ground motion boundary based on observed
390 amplification patterns in NGA-East residuals. Levandowski and McNamara (2024) expanded on
391 this approach by picking inflections in Lg-amplitude vs. distance profiles on Gulf Coast-CEUS
392 boundary-crossing raypaths. In both studies, the delineated boundary approximately tracks the
393 northern edge of thick sediments (>3 km) and coincides with a noticeable Q_0 gradient in our map.
394 Similarly, Chapman and Guo (2021) proposed a seismic response-based boundary informed by
395 sediment thickness transitions and observed ground motion differences during CEUS events. In
396 our Q_0 model (Fig. 6), a clear attenuation boundary aligns closely with this zone, separating high-
397 Q_0 interior crust ($Q_0 \sim 300-330$) from the more attenuating sediments of the GCP ($Q_0 \sim 200-270$).

398 Across the Coastal Plain, sediment thickness varies from less than 1 km near the boundary with
399 the Piedmont to more than 12–15 km near the Gulf Coast and parts of the ME (Laske and Masters,
400 1997; Chapman and Guo, 2021). This thickening trend is crucial, as the sediment column acts as
401 a low-Q waveguide that enhances both intrinsic and scattering attenuation of regional Lg phases.

402 In the GCP, Q_0 values drop to $\sim 200-220$ in the central and northern Gulf region, values comparable
403 to those seen in tectonically active areas like the Basin and Range Province in the WUS. This is
404 striking given the intraplate tectonic setting of the CEUS, and likely reflects the combined effects
405 of high porosity, fluid-rich sediments, and moderately elevated heat flow (up to ~ 80 mW/m² in the
406 northern GCP; Blackwell and Richards, 2004). It is also a known region of crustal thinning
407 associated with the opening of the Gulf (Keller et al., 2016). Farther south toward the Gulf,
408 attenuation and heat flow both decrease. This spatial pattern is supported by the attenuation maps
409 of Gallegos et al. (2014), who observed similar Lg Q_0 values in this region and interpreted them
410 as a product of combined thermal and sedimentary influences.

411 In the ACP, attenuation remains moderate to high, though with greater spatial variability compared
412 to the GCP. A prominent Q_0 low (230–250) is observed across coastal South Carolina, coinciding
413 with several significant seismic and geologic features. Notably, this includes the 2021–2024 Elgin-
414 Lugoff seismic swarm (Adeboboye et al., 2025), a sequence of low-to-moderate magnitude
415 earthquakes that drew renewed attention to the region’s seismicity. Also captured within this low-
416 Q_0 zone is the Middleton Place–Summerville seismic zone, the source region of the ~M7.0 (e.g.,
417 Cramer and Boyd, 2014) 1886 Charleston earthquake, one of the most destructive earthquakes in
418 eastern North America. Additionally, the low- Q_0 anomaly spans areas associated with the Florence
419 Seismic Zone and may extend toward the Cape Fear Arch, a tectonic structure thought to reflect
420 reactivated Paleozoic sutures and coastal flexure. These zones are collectively underlain by thick,
421 unconsolidated to semi-consolidated sedimentary layers and cut by numerous buried faults inferred
422 from seismic reflection data, and topographic lineaments (Marple and Hurd, 2021). Despite these
423 compelling correlations, raypath coverage in the ACP is inherently limited due to the region’s
424 relatively low background seismicity and the edgeward placement of many stations particularly
425 impacting west-to-east Lg propagation. As such, while the observed attenuation anomaly aligns
426 spatially with multiple geologically and seismically active structures, caution should be exercised
427 in interpreting its finer-scale character.

428 Florida (except the western panhandle) appears to have lower attenuation (higher Q) that is more
429 consistent with mid-continental Q in our results. Being on the edge of our tomographic study
430 limits what can be interpreted from our results. But this higher Q in Florida agrees with the Q
431 observations of Cramer (2018) that the unique carbonate geology of Florida is less attenuating than
432 the GCP. Also, as pointed out by Cramer (2018), the mid-continent like lower attenuation extends
433 from Florida through Georgia and central and northern Alabama, consistent with lower attenuation
434 north of the AOL than south of the AOL (Figure 6b).

435 Smaller high-attenuation regions are also present in the central and northern Appalachians (Figure
436 6). The central Appalachian feature is just to the west of the APC in Pennsylvania, Delaware, and
437 Virginia. The Central Appalachian Anomaly (CAA) in the upper mantle has been identified from
438 seismic and electrical observations below the Virginia and West Virginia border region (Mittal et
439 al., 2023) and is associated with a shallowing of the asthenosphere to 100 km in that region. The
440 seismic attenuation feature observed in this study, located northeast of the CAA, may be related to

441 the CAA itself. Our crustal Q feature seems well resolved by our tomography, but maybe offset
442 due to its small size, the spatial resolution limit of our 50 km tomography grid, and possibly an
443 offset to the NE of this thermal mantle anomaly's effect on the crust, perhaps due to spatial patterns
444 of crustal thinning and fault geometries.

445 The northern Appalachian seismic attenuation anomaly in New England and SE Canada consists
446 of a very small $Q < 250$ features along the St. Lawrence River in Canada amid a broader $Q = 250$ -
447 300 region in northern New England. These low- Q features are along the seismic zones along the
448 St. Lawrence River and western Quebec between Charlevoix and Montreal and extending to
449 Ottawa. The extension of this feature into northern New York could be related to the Adirondack-
450 Western Quebec seismicity zone identified by Yang and Aggarwal (1981). The Northern
451 Appalachian Anomaly (NAA) in seismic and possibly electrical properties is centered on
452 Massachusetts, New Hampshire, and Vermont with a 400 km diameter at 200 km depth in the
453 mantle (Menke et al., 2016; Kim and Evans, 2022). The NAA is attributed to small-scale
454 upwelling related to an eddy in the asthenospheric flow (Menke et al., 2016). The portion of our
455 higher seismic crustal attenuation feature in New England extending south and east of the St.
456 Lawrence and Adirondack-Western Quebec seismic zones is over and to the NE of the mantle
457 NAA, possibly due in part to being on the edge of our ray path coverage, to the predominant NE
458 azimuth of our ray paths in New England, and to lateral offsets in the crustal effects of the NAA.

459 Overall, our attenuation results support a clear distinction between the high- Q_0 , stable crust of the
460 Midcontinent CEUS and the more attenuating, sediment-rich Coastal Plains. The transition
461 between these regions is marked by abrupt lateral gradients in Q_0 , coincident with changes in
462 crustal composition, thermal structure, and sediment thickness. While the ME bridges the two
463 domains with similar low- Q_0 characteristics, it is a unique tectonic feature and not entirely
464 representative of either province. Together, these findings emphasize the need to treat the Coastal
465 Plain as a distinct seismic response region within the CEUS, one that shares attenuation
466 characteristics with tectonically active western basins, despite its intraplate location.

467

468

469 3.4 Receiver Terms (Site Response)

470 Local, shallow geologic site conditions significantly influence the amplitude of Lg waves,
471 contributing to observed variability in recorded ground motions across stations. In our joint
472 inversion framework, site response is captured by the frequency- and station-specific term
473 $\ln(R_i(f))$, estimated independently at each frequency and for each component (Fig. S7 & S8).
474 Due to data selection thresholds requiring a minimum of four high-quality raypaths per component
475 per station, more stations met criteria for vertical components than for horizontal ones, and
476 discussion initially focuses on the average vertical R terms (Fig. 8a).

477 There is a first-order contrast between relative damping in the WUS ($\ln(R)<0$) and amplification
478 in the midcontinent CEUS ($\ln(R)>0$). Some of the largest midcontinent amplifications are found
479 in Oklahoma, broadly along both the western and eastern arms of the MCR, and in the
480 northernmost ME, where $\ln(R)$ approaches 1. The presence of sedimentary basins ~1–5 km thick
481 is a commonality among these high- R regions. In the midcontinent, damping observed in areas of
482 Ontario, the northern Appalachians, and the northern Great Plains are exceptions, with $\ln(R)<0$.
483 These areas are mostly characterized by exposed or shallow bedrock, limiting potential resonance

484 Site response is highly variable across the Coastal Plains. Sediments of the ACP appear to amplify
485 shaking, with R values 0.2–0.7 along the ACP and easternmost GCP. Counterintuitively, on the
486 GCP R generally decreases from north to south: positive $\ln(R)$ characterizes the northern GCP and
487 ME as sediment thickness approaches 0 and Q_0 reaches a local minimum, yet $\ln(R)$ values of ~-
488 0.3 are common farther south toward the Gulf as sediment thickens and Q_0 increases modestly.
489 Overall, we find poor correspondence between sediment thickness and site response in the Gulf
490 Coast.

491 To facilitate a more physically meaningful comparison of site effects across the CEUS, we present
492 the ratio between horizontal and vertical site terms (i.e., $H/V = \ln(R_H) - \ln(R_v)$), offering an
493 approximate spectral proxy for horizontal site amplification relative to vertical response (Fig. 8c).
494 H/V ratios are only mapped where both vertical and horizontal site terms were independently
495 estimated.

496 Our H/V results reveal spatially coherent, prominent horizontal amplification in the GCP, ACP,
497 and ME. These regions are characterized by positive H/V values, indicating that horizontal ground
498 motions are systematically amplified relative to vertical motions. This behavior is consistent with
499 the expectation from prior modeling and empirical studies (Furumura and Kennett, 1997; Chapman
500 and Guo, 2021) that unconsolidated or partially saturated sediments tend to preferentially amplify
501 horizontal energy. Within the GCP, horizontal over vertical amplification is widespread, with H/V
502 values ranging from +0.2 to +0.5 ln-units. This region's thick, flat-lying sediment accumulations,
503 elevated porosity, and fluid content contribute to intrinsic and scattering attenuation mechanisms
504 that disproportionately affect vertical energy, allowing horizontal waves to dominate at the surface.
505 The trend continues eastward into the ACP, where the pattern of horizontal amplification persists
506 along the fall line and coastal margins. This polarity shift from positive H/V in the Coastal Plain
507 to negative values in the interior sharply delineates the Coastal Plain boundary, reinforcing its
508 geophysical expression in site response behavior.

509 In contrast, parts of the Midcontinent CEUS experience relatively greater amplification of
510 vertically polarized Lg energy than horizontally polarized, including the Ozark Plateaus, Interior
511 Low Plateaus (central Kentucky and Tennessee); the Valley and Ridge and Blue Ridge from the
512 southern Appalachian Mountains to the New Jersey/New York area, the Adirondacks, and
513 southern Ontario. These regions all have a history of tectonism and deformation—specifically
514 sharing history of orogenesis under horizontal compression—resulting in near-surface geologic
515 structures that are very different from the flat-lying strata of the Coastal Plains. Examining
516 vertically polarized Lg from the 2011 Mineral, VA earthquake sequence, McNamara et al. (2014)
517 noted systematically ~33% higher Q for raypaths that paralleled the Appalachians than for those
518 that crossed the range. Cramer and Powell (2021) noted similar patterns from the 2020 Sparta, NC
519 earthquake, attributing the energy loss on range-crossing raypaths to scattering as waves crossed
520 the structural grain and specifically the dipping foliation inherited from Paleozoic orogenesis.
521 Nevertheless, McNamara et al. (2014) described a more profound ~300% difference for
522 horizontally polarized S-waves (SH): Q_0 110 for SH-waves travelling NW–SE across the grain
523 compared to Q_0 305 for NE–SW paths. These findings suggest that steeply dipping tectonic fabrics
524 and lateral contrast in lithology preferentially deaden horizontally polarized energy. Therefore,
525 inherited uppermost crustal fabrics and lateral contrasts are two possible explanations for the

526 relatively greater vertical amplifications compared to horizontal in these tectonized areas. By
527 comparison, horizontally polarized waves in the flat-lying, laterally continuous Coastal Plain strata
528 do not encounter substantial lateral contrasts or cross sub-vertical foliations, preserving their
529 horizontal amplitudes, while vertically polarized energy repeatedly crosses the layer-cake
530 impedance contrasts and loses amplitude.

531 The spatial gradient in H/V site response across the CEUS underscores the interplay between near-
532 surface geology and ground motion amplification. Because the average $\ln(R)$ across stations is
533 normalized near zero due to our inversion framework, the range of absolute values of $\ln(R)$ from
534 approximately -1.5 to $+1.5$ \ln units (Fig. 8, S7 & S8) correspond to a variation in amplification
535 factors from ~ 0.22 to ~ 4.5 times the reference amplitude. This yields a 20-fold difference in
536 possible site amplification between the most extreme damping and amplification conditions.
537 Putting this effect into context, we consider that Levandowski et al. (2021) found that source
538 amplitudes S increase by ~ 2 \ln -units per M_w -unit. Consistent with their findings, our results also
539 demonstrate that $\ln(S)$ scales linearly with M_w at a similar rate (~ 2 \ln -units per M_w -unit), as shown
540 in Figure S9. The Lg waves generated by a $M_w 6$ event are ~ 3 \ln -units greater in amplitude than
541 those from a $M_w 4.5$. By extension, a hard-rock site with $\ln(R) -1.5$ at some distance from a
542 magnitude $M_w 6$ event might experience similar shaking to a high-amplification site with $\ln(R)$
543 $+1.5$ that is the same distance from a $M_w 4.5$ earthquake. These site effects emphasize the critical
544 role of local geology in shaping ground motion patterns and have direct implications for accurate
545 seismic hazard assessment in the CEUS. While a detailed analysis of source scaling is beyond the
546 scope of this study, Figure S10 presents the spatial distribution of residual source terms at 0.7 Hz,
547 highlighting regional variability and potential deviations from the average magnitude-scaling
548 trend.

549 The consistency of site terms across all five frequencies for both horizontal and vertical (as shown
550 in supplementary Figures S7 and S8) reinforces the physical robustness of the results. Despite the
551 inversion for each frequency being performed independently, we observe minimal frequency-
552 dependent variability in the ranking or polarity of receiver terms. This repeatability, combined
553 with the fact that most stations recorded dozens to hundreds of events, adds significant confidence
554 to the interpretation of spatial patterns observed in the H/V ratio.

555 4. Model Resolution Tests

556 4.1 Feature Recovery

557 To assess the robustness and resolving capability of our inversion framework, we conducted a
558 series of synthetic feature recovery tests, closely following the methodology of Levandowski et al.
559 (2021), but adapted to the CEUS-specific source-receiver geometry and attenuation patterns
560 resolved in our study (Fig. 9 & Fig. S4). These tests evaluate whether our inversion, with the
561 current station-event configuration and regularization scheme, can reliably recover geologically
562 plausible Q structures. We constructed a synthetic Q model containing first-order east–west
563 contrasts and second- to third-order attenuation features consistent with our observed results. The
564 input model included high-attenuation anomalies in the Basin and Range; the Gulf Coast, SOA,
565 and ME; and a northeast-trending attenuation corridor from the eastern margin of the MCR through
566 western Ohio into the Appalachian foreland. Additional low- Q anomalies were embedded in the
567 ACP near South Carolina, the northeast CEUS (New England region), and along the eastern edge
568 of Basin & Range (i.e., the Wasatch Front). The model also featured high- Q anomalies in Central
569 Texas, the Midcontinent, and the Colorado Plateau, while the background Q was set to ~ 270 in the
570 western U.S. and ~ 350 in the CEUS.

571 The inversion successfully recovers the majority of target features. Prominent structures such as
572 the ME, Gulf Coast anomaly, and high- Q zones in the Colorado Plateau and central Texas are
573 distinctly imaged. The northeast-trending low- Q anomaly across the Appalachian foreland and the
574 New England anomaly in the northeastern CEUS are also recovered with meaningful spatial
575 continuity. The only notable exception is the South Carolina low- Q patch, which was not reliably
576 recovered, likely due to limited raypath density in that region, as confirmed by our ray coverage
577 diagnostics. The latter suggests that if there is a high-attenuation region in South Carolina, its Q
578 could be even lower than our tomography shows.

579 The fact that even the $\pm 10\%$ perturbations to the input Q are partially reconstructed in most areas
580 suggests that our model is sensitive to lateral variations on the order of tens of Q units over
581 distances of ~ 100 km. These results confirm that, particularly in areas of dense sampling, the
582 inversion framework is capable of resolving second- and third-order attenuation features with
583 physical significance.

584 4.2 Checkerboard Resolution Tests

585 To evaluate the spatial resolving power of our inversion framework, we performed checkerboard
586 tests using a synthetic Q model composed of alternating high- and low- Q anomalies with $100 \times$
587 100 km block dimensions, embedded in a background Q of 300. High- Q regions were assigned
588 values of 350, and low- Q blocks were set to 250. The synthetic amplitude dataset was generated
589 using the real 0.7 Hz station-event geometry and inverted with the same SVD algorithm and
590 regularization parameters used in the main tomography (Fig. 10, Fig S5 & S6).

591 The results of the checkerboard tests (Fig. 10) demonstrate that the inversion recovers most of the
592 100×100 km features across the CEUS and parts of the western U.S., with notable differences
593 between vertical and horizontal components. The vertical-component recovery shows high fidelity
594 across nearly the entire model domain, successfully imaging alternating anomalies in regions
595 associated with key features discussed in our main model, including the ME, SOA, MCR, Central
596 Texas, Colorado Plateau, and GCP. Resolution is somewhat reduced in the ACP, particularly along
597 the southeastern seaboard, though major blocks remain identifiable, and anomaly polarity is
598 preserved. The horizontal-component checkerboard test yields broadly consistent recovery in most
599 parts of the Midcontinent CEUS, particularly in the ME, SOA, and parts of Southern Great Plains.
600 However, resolution degrades in the Coastal Plain, where lower path density and fewer horizontal-
601 component records reduce inversion sensitivity.

602 The strong recovery of 100 km anomalies across key geologic provinces confirms that the CEUS-
603 focused station and event distribution provides sufficient resolution to image both broad and
604 intermediate-scale structures in vertical-component Q . Following the approach of Levandowski et
605 al. (2021), these checkerboard tests further validate that all second- and third-order attenuation
606 features highlighted in our tomographic results are indeed within the resolving power of this
607 dataset.

608 4.3 Model Uncertainty

609 To assess the robustness of our tomographic inversion results, we evaluated model uncertainties
610 using jackknife-down sampling of events. In each of 100 jackknife realizations, approximately \sqrt{N}
611 events were randomly excluded from the inversion, where N is the total number of unique events.

612 This follows the classical jackknife resampling approach (Efron and Tibshirani, 1993), ensuring
613 robustness by capturing the variability introduced by different event subsets. For each realization,
614 the full inversion workflow was repeated independently, and the distributions of Q values across
615 all realizations were used to quantify uncertainty at each node and frequency. From these,
616 frequency-dependent Q values were regressed to estimate Q_0 and η for each jackknife run, enabling
617 us to compute standard deviations for both parameters across the CEUS.

618 The standard deviation (σ) of Q_0 for the vertically polarized model is shown in Figure 11a. The
619 majority of the model shows low uncertainty ($\sigma < 3$), particularly in well-sampled regions like the
620 Midcontinent, Southern Great Plains, and Gulf Coast. Given a typical Q_0 value of ~ 300 , this
621 corresponds to relative uncertainties of approximately 1–2%, indicating excellent model stability.
622 Slightly elevated σ values (~ 4 – 7 Q units) occur in more poorly sampled zones, including parts of
623 the northeastern U.S. and western margin, but even in these areas, the uncertainty remains modest
624 when compared to the magnitude of resolved anomalies, which are 10s of Q units.

625 Uncertainty in η , the frequency dependence parameter, which also remains low ($\sigma < 0.004$) across
626 most of the model domain (Fig.11b). Higher uncertainty values (~ 0.007 – 0.010) are primarily
627 confined to the northeastern part of the study region, reflecting decreased resolution in these areas.
628 These patterns are consistent with lower raypath density, as also observed in our checkerboard and
629 feature recovery tests. Again, even these < 0.01 -unit uncertainties are small compared to the
630 systematic ~ 0.05 -unit differences among provinces, which are discussed next.

631

632 **5.0 Discussion**

633 **5.1. Frequency Dependence of Attenuation**

634 To synthesize the multi-frequency attenuation results, we examine the spatial variation of
635 frequency dependence, denoted η , as derived from the power-law relationship as equation 2.4
636 Although this empirical formulation lacks a strict physical basis (Pasyanos, 2013), it remains a
637 widely used diagnostic for characterizing variations in attenuation behavior across regions and

638 identifying the relative roles of scattering and intrinsic attenuation mechanisms (e.g., Mayeda et
639 al., 1992; Phillips et al., 2014; Levandowski et al., 2021).

640 Our η model, computed from frequency-dependent inversions for vertical, horizontal and joined
641 datasets, reveals coherent patterns across components, indicating stability in the derived frequency
642 dependence (Fig. 7 & Fig. S1b). The interpretation below is based on the vertical-component
643 model, which offers greater resolution (Fig. 7a).

644 The observed η values across the CEUS vary from ~ 0.7 to 1.05, with clear regional trends. High-
645 attenuation regions such as the Gulf Coast and margins of the Colorado Plateau exhibit the highest
646 η values (~ 0.95 –1.05), indicating a strong frequency dependence. In contrast, stable cratonic
647 interiors, particularly the Mid-Continent CEUS and parts of the Permian Basin—exhibit η values
648 closer to 0.7–0.8, consistent with a more uniform, low-attenuation crust (Fig. 7).

649 This spatial trend aligns with theoretical expectations: scattering attenuation is generally more
650 frequency-dependent than intrinsic attenuation, with $\eta > 0.9$ indicative of strong scattering effects,
651 while $\eta < 0.8$ typically reflects dominant intrinsic energy loss (Mayeda et al., 1992). Consequently,
652 our results suggest that the margins of the Gulf Coast and Colorado Plateau are strongly influenced
653 by scattering from structural heterogeneities (e.g., steep faults, lateral contrasts, changes in crustal
654 thickness), whereas the Midcontinent CEUS exhibits lower scattering contributions and more
655 uniform intrinsic attenuation. These interpretations are further supported by the observed spatial
656 correlation between high η and low Q_0 values implying that areas of strong frequency dependence
657 tend to coincide with zones of high overall attenuation.

658 A particularly striking feature in our η model is the sharp gradient along the CEUS-Coastal Plain
659 boundary, which separates high- η values (>0.9) in the sediment-rich Coastal Plains from lower- η
660 interiors (<0.8). This transition reinforces the attenuation contrast discussed in earlier sections and
661 highlights the frequency-dependent nature of seismic wave propagation across the crustal
662 transition from stable crystalline basement to younger, unconsolidated sediments (Cramer, 2018;
663 Chapman and Guo, 2021). Near this boundary, η is high and Q_0 is especially low, yet sediments
664 remain thin compared to more coastal areas. This suggests that intrinsic attenuation within the
665 sedimentary column is not responsible for the observed anomalies. Instead, we suggest that these

666 localized anomalies are the result of scattering of energy as it crosses the structural boundary
667 between cratonic CEUS and extended Coastal Plains. . In the central and eastern Gulf Coast Plain
668 (Arkansas, Mississippi, Alabama, and Florida panhandle), this sharp gradient corresponds to the
669 Gulf Coast attenuation boundary delineated by Cramer (2018) and Levandowski and McNamara
670 (2024) and seems related to the Alabama-Oklahoma Lineament (Cebull et al., 1976; Thomas,
671 1976, 1977).

672 Although η provides useful first-order insight into the relative balance of intrinsic and scattering
673 attenuation, it cannot, uniquely separate the two mechanisms on its own. For more rigorous
674 discrimination, techniques such as Multiple Lapse Time Window Analysis or coda-normalization
675 methods must be employed (e.g., Hoshiaba et al., 1991; Fehler et al., 1992; Mahanama et al., 2024).
676 Nevertheless, our spatially resolved η model serves as a valuable proxy for identifying candidate
677 regions where scattering likely dominates, guiding future high-resolution analyses.

678 **5.2. CEUS Tomography – Comparison with Other Studies**

679 Several previous studies have investigated crustal attenuation across the CEUS, employing diverse
680 methodologies, frequency ranges, and spatial resolutions. Foundational efforts such as Erickson et
681 al. (2004), Baqer and Mitchell (1998), and Pasyanos (2013) provided early insights into attenuation
682 structure but were limited by regional scope, sparse data coverage, or simplified modeling
683 assumptions. Among these, Gallegos et al. (2014) stands out for its focus on the CEUS using Lg
684 Q tomography via two-station and reverse two-station methods, providing high-resolution
685 attenuation maps that offer a direct basis for comparison with our work. Eulenfeld and Wegler
686 (2017) applied the Qopen method to over 25,000 local and regional earthquakes, generating the
687 first nationwide maps of intrinsic and scattering attenuation at high frequencies. While their
688 approach differs from Lg-based tomography, their findings of strong scattering attenuation in the
689 southeastern U.S. and spatial variability in site amplification align with key patterns observed in
690 our results. More recently, Levandowski et al. (2021) employed a joint inversion framework using
691 vertical Lg amplitudes to characterize attenuation across the WUS/CEUS boundary. While their
692 focus was primarily on the western transition zone, their inversion methodology forms the
693 foundation for our study. We adopt and extend this framework across a more uniformly distributed

694 CEUS dataset with higher station-event density, improving spatial resolution and enabling
695 refinement of previously reported attenuation patterns.

696 Erickson et al. (2004) applied a SVD approach to Lg amplitudes measured in the time-domain in
697 one-octave bands (0.75–12 Hz) and solved simultaneously for Q, source, and site terms: a method
698 aligned with our framework. However, their study aggregated data into seven broad physiographic
699 provinces, resulting in coarse Q estimates. Reported average Q_0 values for the Central U.S. (~ 640
700 ± 225) are broadly consistent with the upper end of our Midcontinent estimates (~ 300 – 330),
701 though their Northeast U.S. values ($\sim 645 \pm 143$) are substantially higher than those in our model.
702 Atkinson and Boore (2014) used Fourier amplitude decay with distance at rock sites for New
703 England and SE Canada to estimate crustal attenuation with $Q_0 = 525$ and frequency dependence
704 η as 0.45. Eastern Canada Lg Q estimates are 900–1100 for Q_0 and ~ 0.2 for η (Hasegawa, 1985;
705 Chun et al., 1987), which are higher than eastern US estimates. Baqer and Mitchell (1998), using
706 stacked ratios of Lg coda waves, mapped Q_0 across the U.S., reporting values as high as 650–750
707 in the northern Appalachians and Central Lowlands, intermediate values (400–500) in the Gulf
708 and southern Atlantic Coastal Plains, and lower Q_0 (250–300) in tectonically active western
709 regions. While their spatial trends align broadly with our results, the Q_0 values are significantly
710 higher, likely reflecting methodological differences including the use of coda Q and limited
711 regional event coverage. Pasyanos (2013) implemented multi-phase (Pn, Pg, Sn, Lg) attenuation
712 tomography to image Q_s across North America. Although his Gulf Coast ($Q_0/Q_{3\text{Hz}} \sim 75/175$) and
713 Central Plains ($Q_0/Q_{3\text{Hz}} \sim 415/1000$) values exhibit similar spatial patterns to ours, his broader
714 tectonic focus and major differences in regularization complicate direct comparisons. Collectively,
715 these studies reinforce the general regional structure of crustal attenuation, while differences in
716 methodology and model resolution may explain most discrepancies in absolute Q_0 estimates.

717 A more direct comparison can be made with Gallegos et al. (2014), who applied two-station and
718 reverse two-station Lg Q tomography across the central U.S. between $\sim 105^\circ\text{W}$ and $\sim 80^\circ\text{W}$
719 longitude. Their models consistently resolve high-attenuation zones in the Gulf Coast, ME,
720 Reelfoot Rift, and SOA, features that also emerge prominently in our results. Additionally, their
721 reverse two-station model identified a broad high- Q_0 anomaly across central Texas, consistent
722 with our low-attenuation zone captured in vertical-component inversions. Both of their models
723 delineate an east-northeast-trending high- Q_0 band northwest of the MCR, a feature we also resolve

724 with greater clarity. However, as noted by Levandowski et al. (2021), Gallegos et al. (2014)'s
725 models exhibit lateral Q_0 variations of nearly 1,000 units over distances of less than 100 km, and
726 there are discrepancies in the location and magnitude of anomalies between their two approaches
727 (i.e., two-station and reverse two-station). By contrast, our application of the joint inversion
728 framework adopted from Levandowski et al., combined with a denser CEUS-specific dataset and
729 improved path coverage produces more geologically consistent and spatially coherent attenuation
730 patterns. This may be because our model benefits from improved coverage in the ACP and
731 northeastern CEUS thanks to expanded seismic networks, regions poorly constrained in Gallegos
732 et al. (2014) due to sparse raypath density available from pre-TA seismic networks.

733 Eulenfeld and Wegler (2017) presented the first large-scale maps separating intrinsic and
734 scattering attenuation of high-frequency shear waves (1–20 Hz) across the contiguous United
735 States, utilizing the Qopen method with over 25,000 events recorded by the USArray
736 Transportable Array. Their approach allows for frequency-dependent inversion of intrinsic and
737 scattering attenuation from energy envelopes, while also estimating site amplification and source
738 spectral parameters. They found a clear west-to-east decrease in intrinsic attenuation, reflecting
739 the transition from younger, thermally active crust in the west to older, colder lithosphere in the
740 east. In contrast, scattering attenuation was higher in the eastern U.S., with especially high values
741 in the southern Appalachian Highlands and Interior Low Plateaus, a pattern broadly consistent
742 with elevated crustal heterogeneity in those regions. While their interpolation covers the full U.S.,
743 their CEUS results, particularly in the Central Lowlands and Coastal Plain, are affected by lower
744 event density and sparse ray coverage. Still, high scattering and site amplification observed in the
745 southern CEUS support key patterns that we also resolve. Their work complements our study by
746 offering an independent decomposition of attenuation mechanisms and highlighting the regional
747 variability of wavefield complexity. However, their Qopen framework, based on envelope fitting
748 and 1-D radiative transfer theory, differs from our Lg-based amplitude tomography, and direct
749 comparisons of Q values should be made cautiously given methodological differences and
750 frequency bands used.

751 Levandowski et al. (2021) conducted a broad Lg attenuation tomography study centered on the
752 transition between the Central and Western United States, extending westward into the Basin and
753 Range and eastward to approximately the ME. Their results show strong attenuation ($Q_0 \sim 90$) at

754 the boundary between the Colorado Plateau and Basin and Range, consistent with localized
755 scattering. We observe a comparable low- Q_0 anomaly along this transition zone in our vertical-
756 component map. Other similarities include focused attenuation in the southern Rockies ($Q_0 \sim 110$ –
757 130), which Levandowski et al. interpreted as a possible zone of partial crustal melt, and elevated
758 Q_0 values in the Wyoming Craton and Colorado Plateau interior ($Q_0 \sim 230$ – 250), also present in
759 our results. While their study emphasized resolving contrasts across the WUS/CEUS boundary,
760 their limited path coverage east of $\sim 90^\circ\text{W}$ restricted their resolution in the CEUS interior.

761 Additionally, although Levandowski et al. reported an average CEUS Q_0 of ~ 250 , our model
762 reveals more pronounced lateral variation across the region, ranging from ~ 210 in the ME and
763 Gulf Coast to ~ 330 in the Great Plains. These refinements reflect the higher spatial resolution and
764 uniform path coverage afforded by our CEUS-focused network configuration. Taken together, our
765 results validate several key patterns observed by Levandowski et al. while expanding upon them
766 with enhanced resolution across the eastern U.S. yielding a finer-scale attenuation model better
767 suited for seismic hazard assessment and ground motion prediction in the CEUS.

768 **6.0 Conclusion**

769
770 We present a new high-resolution model of crustal (Lg) attenuation and site amplification across
771 the CEUS and its surroundings, leveraging a dense and geographically extensive dataset compiled
772 from EarthScope TA, the N4 network, and a range of regional and permanent seismic networks.
773 Our approach applies joint tomographic inversion to vertical and horizontal Lg amplitude
774 observations spanning five frequencies, offering the most spatially resolved imaging of attenuation
775 structure across this intraplate region to date. The resulting model reveals consistent regional
776 attenuation patterns that validate and refine prior findings, while also illuminating new features
777 with critical implications for seismic hazard assessment.

778 Our results confirm strong lateral variations in Q_0 across the CEUS, with particularly low
779 attenuation in regions such as the Midcontinent and Central Texas ($Q_0 \sim 360$ – 380), and high
780 attenuation along the GCP margin and ME ($Q_0 \sim 200$ – 230). These low- Q_0 regions exhibit strong
781 frequency dependence ($\eta > 0.9$), consistent with enhanced scattering across the structural

782 boundaries between the stable CEUS and extended regions, failed-rift basins, and crustal fluids. In
783 contrast, the high- Q_0 interiors are marked by weaker frequency dependence ($\eta \sim 0.7\text{--}0.8$),
784 indicative of more uniform, thermally stable crust with low intrinsic attenuation. The gradient in
785 η therefore offers one proxy for the Midcontinent-Coastal Plain boundary that complements
786 boundary delineations based on Q_0 .

787 Sharp lateral transitions in Q_0 are observed along the boundaries of the Coastal Plain and within
788 tectonic features such as the SOA, the Midcontinent Rift System, and the Grenville-Appalachian
789 margin. These boundaries are often accompanied by gradients in η , suggesting a transition from
790 scattering-dominated to intrinsic attenuation regimes. There is a gradient in η along the Alabama-
791 Oklahoma Lineament that does not follow the boundary of the uppermost ME but rather follows
792 the Gulf Coast boundary of Cramer (2018). However, the New Madrid seismic zone at the northern
793 end of the ME does exhibit higher attenuation on E-W ray paths, possibly due to increased
794 scattering. Notably, our model reveals well-defined high- Q_0 zones in the Colorado Plateau and
795 Permian Basin and a low- Q_0 anomaly in comparatively seismically active South Carolina.
796 Additionally, low- Q_0 crustal zones seem associated with the St. Lawrence River seismic zone, the
797 Adirondack-Western Quebec seismic zone, and possibly both the lithospheric Central and
798 Northern Appalachian Anomalies in seismic velocity and earth resistivity. And lower attenuation
799 in Florida due to the carbonate geology is also suggested.

800 Site amplifications are generally greater in the Midcontinent CEUS than WUS. The highest
801 amplifications broadly coincide with intracratonic basins in Oklahoma, along the Midcontinent
802 Rift, and in the northern ME. Anomalously low CEUS amplifications appear in areas of exposed
803 or shallow bedrock. The ACP experiences more amplification than the Gulf Coastal Plain, which
804 has variable site responses that average near 0. The inclusion of horizontal component data enables
805 us to resolve relative horizontal-to-vertical (H/V) amplification ratios. Sediment-mantled regions
806 including the Atlantic and Gulf Coastal Plains, the ME, Oklahoma, and glaciated portions of the
807 Midcontinent are characterized by significantly greater amplification of horizontal shaking than
808 vertical. By contrast, vertical shaking is relatively greater in ancient orogenic regions with shallow
809 or exposed bedrock. The contrast between $H/V > 0$ and $H/V < 0$ sharply delineates the Coastal Plain
810 margins, providing a third proxy for the boundary location. These observations reinforce the
811 importance of incorporating both attenuation and site effects in regional hazard models.

812 Resolution tests demonstrate that our inversion reliably recovers features at scales of 100 km or
813 larger across most of the study area. Jackknife uncertainty analysis confirms that the Q_0 and η
814 models are robust, with relative uncertainties typically less than 2% in well-sampled regions.
815 Together, these results provide a strong foundation for developing improved path-specific ground
816 motion models.

817 Overall, our study demonstrates that attenuation structure in the CEUS is heterogeneous, with
818 patterns that cannot be adequately captured by broad physiographic or tectonic classifications
819 alone. Instead, regional seismic hazard models should account for the sharp lateral transitions and
820 frequency-dependent effects that influence ground motion propagation. Our findings contribute a
821 refined attenuation and amplification model for the CEUS, directly supporting ongoing efforts to
822 improve the NSHM and better inform risk mitigation for critical infrastructure across eastern North
823 America.

824 **DATA AND RESOURCES:**

825 The seismic data used in this study—including high-quality vertical and horizontal component
826 broadband waveforms and their associated instrument response files—were obtained from the
827 IRIS-DMC and are accessible at <https://service.iris.edu/> (last accessed May 2025). The
828 physiographic province boundaries shown in Figure 1a—including the Coastal Plain boundary and
829 its subdivisions—are derived from the U.S. Geological Survey’s polygon coverage of Fenneman’s
830 Physical Divisions of the United States (1:7,000,000 scale). This dataset classifies regions based
831 on shared topographic, geologic, and geomorphic characteristics and is available via the [USGS](#)
832 [Data Catalog](#) (last accessed June 2025). All map visualizations were created using the Generic
833 Mapping Tools (GMT), available at <https://www.generic-mapping-tools.org/> (last accessed July
834 2025). The study area map shown in Figure 1a incorporates both station and event locations,
835 sourced from IRIS-DMC as noted above. Several supporting figures referenced in this study are
836 available in the Supplemental Material. To reproduce the results, the full dataset is publicly
837 accessible: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15875320>. The MATLAB scripts used for Lg
838 tomography inversions follow the methodology by Levandowski et al. and are available at:
839 <https://github.com/WillLevandowski/LgQTomography>.

840 **Declaration of Competing Interests:** The authors have no competing interests to declare.

841 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS:**

842 The authors gratefully acknowledge the Center for Earthquake Research and Information (CERI)
843 at The University of Memphis and Tetra Tech Inc. for their continued support throughout this
844 research. We also extend our sincere thanks to the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) for funding
845 support under external program grants G24AP00270 and G24AP00280, and to CERI Director Dr.
846 Vadim Levin for his valuable feedback. Additional support from all other contributing sources is
847 also gratefully acknowledged.

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1043 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

1044 **Figure 1: Study Area.** (a) Map showing the spatial distribution of seismic events and stations
1045 used in this study. Events with magnitudes ≥ 3.5 and depths < 30 km, recorded between 2007 and
1046 2024, were obtained from the IRIS catalog. Events located west of -100° longitude are shown as
1047 light red circles, while those within the CEUS are shown as dark red circles. Stations are marked
1048 by green triangles (used in vertical component only) & yellow triangles (used in both vertical and
1049 horizontal components), with each station having at least four associated event–station pairs.
1050 Major physiographic provinces across the CEUS are shown using distinct color fills and labeled
1051 using standard abbreviations: Central Lowland (CL), Coastal Plain (CP), Interior Low Plateaus
1052 (ILP), Appalachian Plateaus (AP), Blue Ridge (BR), Piedmont (PI), Adirondack (AD), Valley and
1053 Ridge (VR), Superior Upland (SU), New England (NE), Ouachita (OU), Ozark Plateaus (OP), and
1054 Great Plains (GP). The physiographic province boundaries are based on the USGS polygon
1055 coverage of Fenneman’s “Physical Divisions of the United States” (1:7,000,000 scale), which
1056 delineates regions by common topography, geology, and geomorphic history ([USGS dataset](#)). The
1057 Coastal Plain boundary is used consistently in subsequent figures for reference. (b) Key
1058 attenuation features labeled on the map include the western arm of the Midcontinent Rift (W-
1059 MCR), eastern arm of the MCR (E-MCR), and its extension, the Fort Wayne Rift (FWR), all
1060 delineated with a dark brown line. Other features include the Southern Oklahoma Aulacogen
1061 (SOA), Mississippi Embayment (ME), Permian Basin (PB), South Carolina anomaly (SC),
1062 Colorado Plateau (CP), Northern Appalachian Anomaly (NAA), Ontario (ON), and Central
1063 Appalachian Anomaly (CAA). The Alabama–Oklahoma Lineament (AOL) is highlighted with a
1064 dashed white line. Additionally, numbered regions represent subdivisions of the Coastal Plain: (1)
1065 West Gulf Coastal Plain, (2) Mississippi Alluvial Plain, (3) East Gulf Coastal Plain, (4) Floridian
1066 section, (5) Sea Island section, and (6) Embayed section.

1067 **Figure 2: Data processing workflow for Lg waves.** (a) Example displacement seismogram after
1068 instrument response removal. The velocity lines (in black) indicate group velocities in km/s; the
1069 noise window is shaded in gray and the Lg signal window in yellow. (b) Amplitude spectra for the
1070 Lg wave and the corresponding noise window. (c) SNR evaluated at five center frequencies, with
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1072 **Figure 3 : Data.** (a) Adjusted amplitudes versus hypocentral distance after correcting for
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1074 Bold colored lines indicate the best semi-log linear fit for each frequency, where the slope is
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1082 **Figure 5: Frequency dependence of the model-wide $Q(f)$ fits shown in Figure 1a.** Q increases
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1084 frequencies.

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1087 and contour intervals drawn every 30 Q units. The Coastal Plain boundary and its subsections are
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1094 **Figure 7: (a) Frequency dependence (η)** of attenuation for vertical components. Colors represent
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1110 The background Q is set to ~ 270 for the western U.S. and ~ 350 for the CEUS. **(b)** Recovered Q
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1117 resolution of all input blocks within the study region. **(c)** Same as (b), but for horizontal
1118 components (0.7Hz).

1119 **Figure 11: Uncertainties** in the net Q_0 model. **(a)** Event-based jackknife resampling was
1120 performed to estimate Q_0 uncertainty, with 100 realizations generated by systematically discarding
1121 subsets of events in each run. This approach avoids bias from retaining specific raypaths at certain
1122 frequencies. **(b)** Same methodology applied to estimate uncertainty in the frequency dependence

- 1123 parameter η . Uncertainties are computed at each model node across all realizations. The Coastal
1124 Plain boundary and its subsections are outlined with a solid black line.

Figure 1: Study Area. (a) Map showing the spatial distribution of seismic events and stations used in this study. Events with magnitudes ≥ 3.5 and depths < 30 km, recorded between 2007 and 2024, were obtained from the IRIS catalog. Events located west of -100° longitude are shown as light red circles, while those within the CEUS are shown as dark red circles. Stations are marked by green triangles (used in vertical component only) & yellow triangles (used in both vertical and horizontal components), with each station having at least four associated event–station pairs. Major physiographic provinces across the CEUS are shown using distinct color fills and labeled using standard abbreviations: Central Lowland (CL), Coastal Plain (CP), Interior Low Plateaus (ILP), Appalachian Plateaus (AP), Blue Ridge (BR), Piedmont (PI), Adirondack (AD), Valley and Ridge (VR), Superior Upland (SU), New England (NE), Ouachita (OU), Ozark Plateaus (OP), and Great Plains (GP). The physiographic province boundaries are based on the USGS polygon coverage of Fenneman’s “Physical Divisions of the United States” (1:7,000,000 scale), which delineates regions by common topography, geology, and geomorphic history ([USGS dataset](#)). The Coastal Plain boundary is used consistently in subsequent figures for reference. **(b)** Key attenuation features labeled on the map include the western arm of the Midcontinent Rift (W-MCR), eastern arm of the MCR (E-MCR), and its extension, the Fort Wayne Rift (FWR), all delineated with a dark brown line. Other features include the Southern Oklahoma Aulacogen (SOA), Mississippi Embayment (ME), Permian Basin (PB), South Carolina anomaly (SC), Colorado Plateau (CP), Northern Appalachian Anomaly (NAA), Ontario (ON), and Central Appalachian Anomaly (CAA). The Alabama–Oklahoma Lineament (AOL) is highlighted with a dashed white line. Additionally, numbered regions represent subdivisions of the Coastal Plain: (1) West Gulf Coastal Plain, (2) Mississippi Alluvial Plain, (3) East Gulf Coastal Plain, (4) Floridian section, (5) Sea Island section, and (6) Embayed section.

Figure 2: Data processing workflow for Lg waves. (a) Example displacement seismogram after instrument response removal. The velocity lines (in black) indicate group velocities in km/s; the noise window is shaded in gray and the Lg signal window in yellow. **(b)** Amplitude spectra for the Lg wave and the corresponding noise window. **(c)** SNR evaluated at five center frequencies, with the applied cutoff threshold shown for data selection.

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Figure 10: Checkerboard resolution test using alternating 100-km-wide rows and columns of high ($Q = 350$) and low ($Q = 250$) anomalies on a uniform $Q = 300$ background. **(a)** Input checkerboard model. **(b)** Recovered model using vertical components (0.7Hz), showing clear resolution of all input blocks within the study region. **(c)** Same as (b), but for horizontal components (0.7Hz).

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Supporting information for
Crustal Attenuation and Site Amplification Across the Central and Eastern United States from Lg Q Tomography

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This supplemental file provides supporting figures referenced in the main manuscript. While only a subset of figures is included in the main text, this supplement contains the full set of Q, checkerboard test results and site term estimates across all five frequencies, including both horizontal and vertical components.

Figure S1: (a) Lg Q₀ tomography derived using both horizontal and vertical components. The color scale is based on fixed quantile intervals, with white indicating the median Q₀ value. Contour intervals are spaced every 30 Q units. (b) Frequency dependence (η) of attenuation estimated from the same dataset. The η map also uses fixed quantile intervals for color mapping, with white representing the median η value. Contours are drawn at 0.05 η intervals. In both panels, the Coastal Plain boundary and its subsections are outlined with a solid black line.

Figure S2: Lg Q tomograms derived using vertical components at five individual frequencies, shown in panels (a–e). Frequencies are labeled accordingly. To facilitate comparison across frequencies, the color scale uses fixed quantile intervals, with the median value consistently represented in white. The Coastal Plain boundary and its subsections are outlined with a solid black line.

Figure S3: Lg Q tomograms derived using horizontal components at five individual frequencies, shown in panels (a–e). Frequencies are labeled accordingly. To facilitate comparison across frequencies, the color scale uses fixed quantile intervals, with the median value consistently represented in white. The Coastal Plain boundary and its subsections are outlined with a solid black line.

Figure S4: Feature recovery test. **(a)** Input synthetic Q model with imposed anomalies in specific regions: Central Texas (440), Southern Appalachians (200), Gulf Coastal Plain (200), Mississippi Embayment (200), Edge of New England (200), Colorado Plateau (430), Basin and Range (205), Midcontinent (440), South Carolina anomaly (220), West Ohio (200), and New Jersey shore (200). Background Q is set to ~ 270 in the western U.S. and ~ 350 in the CEUS. **(b)** Recovered Q model using synthetic data generated at 0.7 Hz with the same source-receiver geometry as the observed dataset. **(c)** Same as (b), but with Gaussian noise added ($\sigma = 0.5$ ln-units). **(d)** Same as (c), with an additional 10% random perturbation applied to the input model. The Coastal Plain boundary and its subsections are outlined with a solid black line in all the panels.

Figure S5: Checkerboard resolution test using vertical component data. **(a)** Input model with alternating 100-km-wide rows and columns of high ($Q = 350$) and low ($Q = 250$) anomalies superimposed on a uniform $Q = 300$ background. **(b–f)** Recovered checkerboard patterns at different central frequencies, as labeled.

Figure S6: Checkerboard resolution test using vertical component data. **(a)** Input model with alternating 100-km-wide rows and columns of high ($Q = 350$) and low ($Q = 250$) anomalies, superimposed on a uniform $Q = 300$ background. **(b)** Recovered checkerboard pattern at 0.7 Hz using the same smoothing parameters as in the actual inversion. **(c)** Recovered pattern at 0.7 Hz with reduced smoothing.

Figure S7: Receiver terms estimated from the site response analysis from vertical components at five central frequencies: **(a)** 0.7 Hz, **(b)** 1.4 Hz, **(c)** 2.8 Hz, **(d)** 5.6 Hz, and **(e)** 11.3 Hz. For each station, site terms were calculated independently at each frequency. The inset in the lower-right corner of each map provides a zoomed-in view of the region outlined by the dashed box, highlighting spatial details in areas of dense station coverage. The purple-shaded region in all panels marks the Coastal Plain.

Figure S8: Receiver terms estimated from the site response analysis from horizontal components at five central frequencies: **(a)** 0.7 Hz, **(b)** 1.4 Hz, **(c)** 2.8 Hz, **(d)** 5.6 Hz, and **(e)** 11.3 Hz. For each station, site terms were calculated independently at each frequency. The inset in the lower-right corner of each map provides a zoomed-in view of the region outlined by the dashed box, highlighting spatial details in areas of dense station coverage. The purple-shaded region in all panels marks the Coastal Plain.

Figure S9: Source terms: The observed linear relationship between empirical $\ln(S)$ and moment magnitude (M_w) supports a proportional scaling between source amplitude and seismic moment, with $\ln(S)$ approximately increasing by ~ 2 M_w units. Linear regression fits are shown for each of the five central frequencies (0.7 Hz, 1.4 Hz, 2.8 Hz, 5.6 Hz, and 11.3 Hz), with corresponding slope values listed in the bottom-right legend.

Figure S10: Spatial distribution of residual source terms at 0.7 Hz. Residuals are defined as the difference between observed $\ln(S)$ and the expected value from the magnitude– $\ln(S)$ regression (fig. S9). These residuals isolate deviations from the average magnitude scaling trend, highlighting events that radiate more (positive residuals) or less (negative residuals) energy than predicted. The variability likely reflects natural differences in source properties. A detailed analysis of magnitude-to-source scaling relationships is beyond the scope of this manuscript.

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